

MEDIATING EFFECTS OF OCCUPATIONAL STRESS ON TEACHER'S PSYCHOSOCIAL SKILLS AND JOB PERFORMANCE IN MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING (MDL)

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ABSTRACT

The main thrust of the study was to assess the level of occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance of public secondary teachers in the districts of Maribojoc, Antequera, Catigbian, Balilihan, and Cortes (MACBAC) in modular distance learning (MDL). Through random sampling, the study involved a total of 119 respondents. Specifically, it presented the respondents' profile on age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service. In assessing the level of teachers' occupational stress, this study focused on occupational role, personal strain, and personal resources. In assessing the respondents' psychosocial skills, it focused on performance skills, interpersonal skills, and self-management skills. In assessing the teachers' job performance, the study employed the documentary analysis using the Annual IPCR results. The study used the weighted mean as the basis for analysis and interpretation of descriptive data. As to findings, the study has a cohort of teachers aged at least 30 years old, females with academic units in a Master's Degree Program, and with a length of service of 6 years at minimum. Moreover, the study revealed less stressful job experience of the respondents in modular distance learning (MDL) based on the overall mean of 2.44, high psychosocial skills based on the overall mean of 3.27, and a very satisfactory job performance based on the mean performance rating of 4.15. The Two-Way Chi-Square Tests revealed the profile on age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service were not significantly related to the level of their occupational stress and psychosocial skills. However, length of service and psychosocial skills were significantly related. Further, by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, the study found the three variables were insignificantly correlated. The study concluded the

respondents were resilient in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL), specifically during the academic year 2021-2022. As an end view, the study proposed an action plan on improving teachers' occupational well-being.

Keywords: *job performance, modular distance learning (MDL), occupational stress, psychosocial skills*

INTRODUCTION

Education is considered the backbone of a civilized society, as it empowers individuals to live by ethical principles and contribute meaningfully to social development and national unity (Ibrahim, 2011). However, the sudden onset of the COVID-19 pandemic brought about unprecedented challenges, disrupting the conventional operations of the education system. Among the most affected were public school teachers, who faced a seismic shift in their professional routines. For instance, many worked until midnight to print and distribute voluminous learning modules, highlighting the burdens imposed by implementing Modular Distance Learning (MDL).

While MDL served as an alternative to ensure academic continuity, it also introduced unique pressures to educators, especially in adapting to technological demands, limited digital infrastructure, and weakened communication between teachers and parents. These circumstances intensified the occupational stress experienced by teachers and significantly affected their psychosocial well-being and job performance. Rahmajati et al. (2022) emphasized that psychological resilience was essential in helping individuals cope with these challenges, highlighting its role in maintaining mental health and sustaining educational efforts during the pandemic.

Psychosocial well-being and social-emotional learning are essential components of effective educational environments, particularly in contexts affected by adversity or crisis. McNatt et al. (2018) emphasize the importance of integrating psychosocial support within educational systems to foster resilience, emotional regulation, and a sense of safety among learners and educators. Their guidance highlights how structured support can help individuals manage stress, strengthen relationships, and create a more inclusive and supportive learning environment. This approach reinforces the idea that psychosocial well-being is not supplementary, but foundational to quality education.

Given this context, exploring the interplay between occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance within the MDL setup is imperative. Numerous studies (e.g., Shen & Slater, 2021; Poysa et al., 2021) have revealed how occupational stress during the pandemic negatively influenced educators' mental health and professional engagement. However, limited literature exists examining the mediating role of occupational stress in the relationship between teachers' psychosocial skills and job performance, particularly within the localized setting of modular distance learning in the Philippine context.

This study was conducted in the First Congressional District of Bohol—covering the districts of Maribojoc, Antequera, Catigbian, Balilihan, and Cortes—during the academic year 2021–2022. It aims to determine whether occupational stress mediates between public secondary school teachers' psychosocial skills and their job performance under MDL. Through this investigation, the researcher seeks to generate evidence-based recommendations and propose an action plan to help reduce occupational stress and enhance teacher well-being and performance amidst alternative modes of instruction.

Research Questions

The main thrust of this study was to assess the level of occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance among public secondary teachers in Maribojoc, Antequera, Catigbian, Balilihan, and Cortes (MACBAC) districts during the academic year 2021-2022. The findings served as the baseline for proposing an action plan.

Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.2 highest educational attainment and
 - 1.3 length of service?
2. What is the level of the respondents' occupational stress in the following dimensions:
 - 2.1 occupational role;
 - 2.2 personal strain; and
 - 2.3 personal resources?
3. What is the level of the respondents' psychosocial skills in the following dimensions:
 - 3.1 performance skills;
 - 3.2 interpersonal skills; and
 - 3.3 self-management skills?
4. What is the level of the respondents' job performance based on their IPCR results for the academic year 20121-2022?
5. Is there a significant degree of relationship between the teachers' profile and the following:
 - 5.1 level of their occupational stress;
 - 5.2 level of their psychosocial skills; and
6. Is there a significant degree of correlation between the following:
 - 6.1 level of the respondents' occupational stress and their psychosocial skills;
 - 6.2 level of the respondents' occupational stress and their job performance; and
 - 6.3 level of the respondents' psychosocial skills and their job performance?
7. Is there a significant degree of variance in the respondents' level of occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment?
8. Based on the findings, what action plan may the study propose?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This quantitative study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design to examine the relationships among the key variables. Additionally, a descriptive-comparative design was employed to identify significant differences in the respondents' levels of occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. Documentary analysis was also conducted to assess the respondents' job performance using relevant performance evaluation records. Data were collected through pilot-tested, structured, and modified questionnaires. The study's findings served as the basis for developing a proposed action plan.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC, which includes the educational districts of Maribojoc, Antequera, Catigbian, Balilihan, and Cortes, during the academic year 2021–2022. These five districts fall under the jurisdiction of the First Congressional District of Bohol. The research involved five public secondary schools: Pagnitoan National High School, Bantolinao National High School, Catigbian National High School, Cong. Pablo Malasarte National High School and Fatima National High School. One secondary school was selected from each district based on the criteria that the school must have a teacher population of at least 20 and no less than 500 student population.

Research Respondents

Using a random sampling technique, the study selected 119 public secondary school teachers from the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC, Bohol, during the academic year 2021–2022. Teachers with less than one year of service in the Department of Education (DepEd) were excluded to ensure that all respondents had experienced traditional and modular teaching modalities within the same school. The sample size was determined using an online sample size calculator, with a 95% confidence level and a 0.05 margin of error.

Distribution of Respondents
n=119

School	Number of Teachers	Sample Size
A	25	17
B	54	38
C	34	24
D	37	26
E	20	14
Total	170	119

Research Instrument

To assess the levels of occupational stress and psychosocial skills among teachers, this study utilized self-made and modified questionnaires validated through pilot testing at Mantacida National High School in Catigbian, Bohol. The reliability of the instruments was confirmed through Cronbach's Alpha analysis, which indicated high internal consistency. The questionnaire consisted of three main parts. The first part gathered demographic information from the respondents, including age, sex, highest educational attainment, and length of service.

RELIABILITY STATISTICS

Occupational Stress			Psychosocial Skills		
Cronbach's Alpha	CA Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	CA Based on Standardized Items	No. of Items
.0.967	0.967	70	.930	936	45

The second part of the instrument focused on assessing the level of teachers' occupational stress based on three major dimensions: Occupational Role, Personal Strain, and Personal Resources. The structure of this questionnaire was developed following the thematic framework of the Occupational Stress Inventory-Revised (OSI-R) by Osipow and Spokane (1985). While no original statements were directly adopted or modified, the questionnaire was designed to reflect the core themes of the OSI-R. Under the Occupational Role dimension, the sub-components included Role Overload, Role Insufficiency, Role Ambiguity, Role Boundary, Responsibility, and Physical Environment. Personal Strain was measured through the sub-dimensions of Vocational, Psychological, Interpersonal, and Physical Strain. Meanwhile, Personal Resources were evaluated based on Recreation, Self-Care, Social Support, and Rational/Cognitive Coping. This part of the questionnaire comprised 14 components, with five items totaling 70 indicators. All items were written in negative form and were rated using a four-point Likert scale: (1) Disagree (Not Stressful), (2) Slightly Agree (Less Stressful), (3) Moderately Agree (Moderately Stressful), and (4) Strongly Agree (Highly Stressful).

The third part of the instrument assessed teachers' psychosocial skills across three dimensions: Performance Skills, Interpersonal Skills, and Self-Management Skills. Each dimension included 15 affirmative statements for a total of 45 items. Responses were rated using the following four-point scale: (1) Not Manifested (Very Low), (2) Rarely Manifested (Low), (3) Sometimes Manifested (Average), and (4) Frequently Manifested (High). The questionnaire items for Performance Skills were adapted from Moreno-Murcia et al. (2015), Interpersonal Skills from Darrow et al. (2014), and Self-Management Skills

from Mezo (2005). The researcher modified all statements to align with the current educational context under the new normal.

To assess teachers' job performance, the study employed documentary analysis. With formal approval from the Public Schools District Supervisors and the school principals, the researcher retrieved the respondents' Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) results for the academic year 2021–2022. An informed consent form was also distributed to all participating teachers to obtain their full permission to use their IPCR ratings in the study.

Research Procedure

Gathering of Data

The researcher first sought formal approval from the Dean of the Graduate School of the University of Bohol and the Vice President for Academic Affairs to conduct the study beyond the university premises. Letters of intent were also sent to the Public Schools Division Superintendent and the School Principals of the identified respondent schools to secure permission to conduct the research. Similarly, a letter was addressed to the School Principal of Mantacida National High School in Mantacida, Catigbian, Bohol, requesting authorization to conduct the pilot study at the said institution.

In the actual conduct of the study, the researcher ensured that all participants voluntarily agreed to participate in the research. Following health and safety protocols during the COVID-19 pandemic, the respondents were given printed copies of the questionnaires, which they answered individually in their respective households. The researcher strictly instructed the teachers not to answer the survey tools in groups to maintain the responses' credibility and minimize physical contact.

The researcher distributed the pilot-tested questionnaires to the selected participants upon receiving the necessary approvals. Before answering the survey, the respondents were briefed on the objectives and procedures of the study. After retrieving the questionnaires, the researcher carefully reviewed each form to ensure all items were completed. The data were then accurately recorded and tabulated to ensure the validity and reliability of the study's findings.

Data Analysis

In the analysis and data interpretation, the researcher used a statistical software called "SPSS24," otherwise known as the Statistical Package for Social Sciences Statistics 24.

Percentage. In determining the quantitative distribution of the respondent's age, sex, highest educational attainment and length of service, the researcher computed the sample percentage.

Weighted Mean/Simple Average. This statistical computation measured the central tendency as it represents the average response of a given data. The researcher computed the weighted mean to determine the respondents' occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance.

For accurate data interpretation, the researcher computed the weighted mean. The researcher sets a hypothetical range using the scale below.

The Level of Teacher's Occupational Stress

Scale	Range	Descriptive Value	Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Stressful
3	2.50 – 3.24	Moderately Agree	Moderately Stressful
2	1.75 – 2.49	Slightly Agree	Less Stressful
1	1.00 – 1.74	Disagree	Not Stressful

The Level of Teacher's Psychosocial Skills

Scale	Range	Descriptive Value	Interpretation
4	3.25 – 4.00	Frequently Manifested	High Psychosocial Skills
3	2.50 – 3.24	Sometimes Manifested	Average Psychosocial Skills
2	1.75 – 2.49	Rarely Manifested	Low Psychosocial Skills
1	1.00 – 1.74	Not Manifested	Very Low Psychosocial Skills

The Level of Teacher's Job Performance

Scale	Range	Adjectival Rating	Interpretation
5	4.500 – 5.000	Outstanding	Performance represents an extraordinary achievement
4	3.500 – 4.499	Very Satisfactory	Performance exceeded expectations
3	2.500 – 3.499	Satisfactory	Performance met expectations
2	1.500 – 2.499	Unsatisfactory	Performance failed to meet expectations
1	1.499 and below	Poor	Performance was consistently below expectations

Tests of Normality. The researcher employed normality tests to determine if the data sets deviate from a normal distribution. Specifically, the researcher will use Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test and Shapiro-Wilk Test to determine if the data on teacher's occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance deviate from a normal distribution or normally distributed.

Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk			Results
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Occupational Stress	.079	119	.065	.979	119	.064	Normal
Psychosocial Skills	.078	119	.073	.984	119	.174	Normal
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk			Results
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.	
Job Performance	.157	119	.000	.906	119	.000	Skewed

Chi-square: The researcher used the Two-way Chi-square test to determine the significant degree of relationship between the respondent's profile and the level of their occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance in modular distance learning (MDL).

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. The researcher computed the value of p in determining the significant degree of correlation of the following variables: Occupational Stress in the three dimensions, Psychosocial Skills in the three dimensions, and Job Performance based on the Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR) results. The study used the parametric statistical method since the data on occupational stress and psychosocial skills were normally distributed. In other words, the data obtained from the two variables did not deviate from normal distributions.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Test. The researcher used the parametric statistical method to determine the significant degree of variance in the respondents' occupational stress and psychosocial skills when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. The researcher used the parametric statistical method since the data on occupational stress and psychosocial skills were normally distributed. In other words, the data obtained from the two variables did not deviate from normal distributions.

Kruskal Wallis Test. The researcher used the Kruskal Wallis Test to determine the variance in the respondents' level of job performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment. The researcher used the non-parametric statistical method since the data on job performance were not normally distributed. In other words, the data of the respondents' teaching performance deviates from a normal distribution or is statistically called "skewed."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter systematically presents the data, analysis, and interpretation according to the sequence of the given specific problems.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents
n = 119

1.1 Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Rank
20 - 29 years old	28	23.53	3.0
30 - 39 years old	44	36.97	1.0
40 - 49 years old	32	26.89	2.0
50 - 59 years old	13	10.92	4.0
60 - 64 years old	2	1.68	5.0
Total	119	100%	
1.2 Sex			
Male	13	10.92	2.0
Female	106	89.08	1.0
Total	119	100%	
1.3 Highest Educational Attainment			
Bachelor's Degree	20	16.81	2.0
With Master's Units	78	65.55	1.0
Master's Degree	17	14.29	3.0
With Doctoral Units	2	1.68	4.5
Doctoral Degree	2	1.68	4.5
Total	119	100%	
1.4 Length of Service			
1 - 5 years	33	27.73	2.0
6 - 10 years	42	35.29	1.0
11 - 20 years	28	23.53	3.0
21 - 30 years	13	10.92	4.0
31 years and above	3	2.52	5.0
Total	119	100%	

In terms of **age**, the largest group of respondents (36.97%) were between 30 to 39 years old, while only 1.68% were aged 60 to 64. This indicates that the teaching workforce in the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC is relatively young and in their prime working years. Younger teachers are often more adaptive to innovations in education, which is crucial in implementing modular distance learning (MDL).

For **sex**, the data show that 89.08% of the respondents were female, confirming the gender imbalance in the teaching profession. This reflects the continuing trend of female dominance in education, particularly in public secondary schools.

Regarding **educational attainment**, the majority (65.55%) had earned academic units in a Master's Degree program. This suggests a strong inclination toward professional growth and further studies among the respondents, which can positively influence teaching quality and career advancement.

As for the **length of service**, most teachers (35.29%) had been in service for 6 to 10 years, while only a few (2.52%) had served for more than 31 years. This suggests that most teachers are experienced yet still early or mid-career, indicating a balance of competence and potential for long-term service.

Table 2.1
Level of Occupational Stress on Occupational Role
n=119

A.1 ROLE OVERLOAD	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. Modular teaching is stressful.	2.91	MA	MS	5
2. The mass production of modules has made me feel exhausted.	3.14	MA	MS	2
3. The distribution and retrieval of modules is time-consuming.	2.96	MA	MS	3
4. Module checking is quite confusing.	2.93	MA	MS	4
5. Lesson feedbacking in modular teaching is very challenging.	3.40	STA	HS	1
Composite Mean	3.07	MA	MS	
A.2 ROLE INSUFFICIENCY	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. I have a hard time with document editing.	2.67	MA	MS	4
2. I am demotivated to teach without my students in the classroom.	2.78	MA	MS	2
3. I feel incapacitated to become a competent teacher.	2.73	MA	MS	3
4. I am demotivated to perform at my best.	2.54	MA	MS	5
5. I have a hard time communicating with the parents of my students.	2.92	MA	MS	1
Composite Mean	2.73	MA	MS	
A.3 ROLE AMBIGUITY	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. I am confused on how to assess my students' learning.	2.96	MA	MS	1
2. I am not confident with modular teaching.	2.92	MA	MS	2
3. I am lost in providing feedback on my students' performance.	2.76	MA	MS	3
4. My superior has appointed me in handling new responsibilities.	2.34	SLA	LS	4
5. My superior did not provide proper guidelines at school.	1.61	D	NS	5
Composite Mean	2.52	MA	MS	
A.4 ROLE BOUNDARY	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. Organizational camaraderie is rarely experienced at my school.	2.11	SLA	LS	1
2. There is a gap between the school administrator/s and teachers.	1.79	SLA	LS	2
3. The administration failed to provide access on communication.	1.61	D	NS	4
4. My school administrator is incompetent in decision-making.	1.48	D	NS	5
5. Supervision at my school seemed to be futile most of the times.	1.68	D	NS	3
Composite Mean	1.73	D	NS	
A.5 RESPONSIBILITY	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. I feel anxious thinking about additional workload.	2.34	SLA	LS	3
2. I care too much about the unfinished business of my colleagues.	2.00	SLA	LS	5
3. I spend much of my time helping my co-teachers in their tasks.	2.03	SLA	LS	4
4. I am pressured of submitting reports beyond the deadline.	2.39	SLA	LS	1
5. Lesson feedbacking has also compromised my free time.	2.35	SLA	LS	2
Composite Mean	2.22	SLA	LS	
A.6 PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. I tried my hardest to comfort myself while on duty.	2.58	MA	MS	2
2. Some of the school facilities are not at their best condition.	2.55	MA	MS	3
3. I start my day dusting and cleaning the classroom.	2.76	MA	MS	1
4. I cannot concentrate on module checking due to unnecessary noise.	1.93	SLA	LS	5
5. I feel physically isolated during working hours.	2.02	SLA	LS	4
Composite Mean	2.37	SLA	LS	
Overall Mean	2.44	Less Stressful		

Parameter:

1.00 - 1.74	Disagree	Not Stressful
1.75 - 2.49	Slightly Agree	Less Stressful
2.50 - 3.24	Moderately Agree	Moderately Stressful
3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Stressful

Table 2.1 presents the level of occupational stress among teachers across the six components of the Occupational Role dimension.

For Role Overload, the highest-rated item was “Lesson feedbacking in modular teaching is very challenging” (WM = 3.40), indicating this aspect as a primary stressor. The composite mean of 3.07 falls under Moderately Stressful, suggesting that while teachers found modular teaching tasks demanding, the absence of classroom behavioral issues may have reduced overall pressure. This supports Nair’s (2017) view that workload contributes significantly to stress, though not to an overwhelming extent in this context.

In Role Insufficiency, the item “I have a hard time communicating with the parents of my students” scored highest (WM = 2.92). The composite mean of 2.73 also indicated a Moderately Stressful level. This suggests that lack of face-to-face interaction disrupted communication and affected teachers’ motivation and perceived competence, echoing global concerns on the limits of distance education.

For Role Ambiguity, the most stressful concern was “I am confused on how to assess my students’ learning” (WM = 2.96). Despite a moderately stressful composite mean of 2.52, teachers disagreed with the idea that their superiors failed to provide proper guidance, implying strong administrative support in adapting to the new teaching setup. This aligns with Bauer and Simmons’ (2000) view that role ambiguity stems from a lack of clear information about responsibilities and expectations, which can hinder confidence and effectiveness in one’s role.

Role Boundary received a composite mean of 1.73 (Not Stressful), with the highest stressor being “Organizational camaraderie is rarely experienced at my school” (WM = 2.11). Overall, teachers felt adequately supported by school leadership, indicating effective communication and decision-making even in the modular setup.

Under Responsibility, the highest-rated item was “I am pressured of submitting reports beyond the deadline” (WM = 2.39). With a composite mean of 2.22 (Slightly Stressful), the findings show that teachers managed responsibilities well, and collaboration among colleagues may have mitigated stress. This slightly contrasts with other studies suggesting workload beyond office hours increases stress.

Lastly, Physical Environment was rated Slightly Stressful (Composite Mean = 2.37), with the task of cleaning classrooms (WM = 2.76) identified as the most stressful. While teachers took on added duties in the absence of students, the quiet and controlled work setting may have contributed to a generally manageable environment, aligning with Shernoff et al.’s (2014) findings that supportive and structured learning environments can positively influence engagement and productivity.

Overall, the composite mean for all six components was 2.44, interpreted as Less Stressful. This indicates that while specific aspects of modular teaching presented challenges, the overall occupational stress level among teachers in the Sub-

Congressional District of MACBAC remained manageable during the modular distance learning setup.

Table 2.1.1
Summary on Teachers' Occupational Stress for Occupational Role
n=119

Components	CM	DV	INT	RANK
1. ROLE OVERLOAD	3.07	MA	MS	1
2. ROLE INSUFFICIENCY	2.73	MA	MS	2
3. ROLE AMBIGUITY	2.52	MA	MS	3
4. ROLE BOUNDARY	1.73	D	NS	6
5. RESPONSIBILITY	2.22	SLA	LS	5
6. PHYSICAL ENVIRONMENT	2.37	SLA	LS	4
Overall Mean	2.44	SLA	Less Stressful	

Table 2.1.1 shows that Role Overload registered the highest composite mean of 3.07, interpreted as Moderately Stressful, while Role Boundary recorded the lowest at 1.73, interpreted as Not Stressful. The overall mean of 2.44 indicates that teachers in the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC generally experienced a less stressful occupational role under modular distance learning (MDL). This supports the findings of Herrmann et al. (2021), who emphasized that enhanced collaboration and environmental adjustments during the pandemic contributed to a more supportive teaching environment.

Table 2.2
Level of Occupational Stress on Personal Strain
n=119

Statement	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1 VOCATIONAL STRAIN				
1. I find it hard providing additional explanation on modular tasks.	2.77	MA	MS	2
2. I am not confident about my students learning.	3.01	MA	MS	1
3. I always seek help from my co-teachers in printing modules.	2.09	SLA	LS	3
4. I feel bored and disinterested to report in school.	1.76	SLA	LS	5
5. I tend to be less productive.	2.05	SLA	LS	4
Composite Mean	2.34	SLA	LS	
2 PSYCHOLOGICAL STRAIN				
	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. I keep on thinking that my pupils are not learning competently.	2.80	MA	MS	2
2. Assessing pupils' performance is for compliance only.	2.29	SLA	LS	5
3. I feel unhappy to those learners who cannot comply requirements.	3.34	STA	HS	1
4. I feel anxious when providing feedback on learners' performance.	2.71	MA	MS	3
5. I am uncertain on how to assess my students' actual performance.	2.60	MA	MS	4
Composite Mean	2.75	MA	MS	Rank
3 INTERPERSONAL STRAIN				
	WM	DV	INT	
1. I prefer to stay apart from my co-teachers while working.	2.25	SLA	LS	3
2. I refrain from having a close contact with my colleagues.	2.06	SLA	LS	5
3. I always make sure that I am at least a meter apart from anybody.	2.37	SLA	LS	2
4. I prefer working at home the entire week.	2.20	SLA	LS	4
5. It seems that modular distance learning divides school unity.	2.47	SLA	LS	1
Composite Mean	2.27	SLA	LS	

4 PHYSICAL STRAIN	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. Module checking is stressful and made me feel exhausted.	2.86	MA	MS	2
2. I see myself gaining weight due to "binge eating."	2.40	SLA	LS	5
3. I have to deal with headache after long hours of using a computer.	2.90	MA	MS	1
4. Making a draft for lesson feedbacking is very compromising.	2.71	MA	MS	4
5. I have to deal with back pains due to long hours of work.	2.86	MA	MS	2
Composite Mean	2.74	MA	MS	
Overall Mean	2.52	Moderately Stressful		

Parameter:

1.00 - 1.74	Disagree	Not Stressful
1.75 - 2.49	Slightly Agree	Less Stressful
2.50 - 3.24	Moderately Agree	Moderately Stressful
3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Stressful

Table 2.2 summarizes teachers' occupational stress under the Personal Strain dimension, which includes vocational, psychological, interpersonal, and physical strain. The overall mean of 2.52 indicates that teachers experienced a Moderate stress level.

For Vocational Strain, the highest concern was a lack of confidence in student learning (WM = 3.01), while disinterest in reporting to school was rated lowest (WM = 1.76). The composite mean of 2.34 indicates a Slightly Stressful level. Despite concerns about learning outcomes, teachers remained motivated and engaged in their duties.

In Psychological Strain, feeling unhappy toward non-compliant learners was the top stressor (WM = 3.34), while viewing assessments as mere compliance had the lowest rating (WM = 2.29). With a composite mean of 2.75, this category was rated as Moderately Stressful, reflecting concerns about the authenticity and effectiveness of student assessments under modular learning.

For Interpersonal Strain, the perception that MDL affects school unity was rated highest (WM = 2.47), but maintaining distance from colleagues was the least stressful (WM = 2.06). The composite mean of 2.27 indicates this area was only Slightly Stressful, suggesting that teachers were able to preserve professional relationships despite limited face-to-face interactions.

Lastly, Physical Strain received a composite mean of 2.74, also interpreted as Moderately Stressful. Headaches due to prolonged computer use were the top concern (WM = 2.90), while weight gain due to stress eating was the least (WM = 2.40). These results show that while teachers experienced some physical discomfort, most managed to cope with the demands of modular teaching.

Table 2.2.1
Summary on Teachers' Occupational Stress for Personal Strain
n=119

Categories	CM	DV	INT	RANK
1. VOCATIONAL STRAIN	2.34	SLA	LS	3
2. PSYCHOLOGICAL STRAIN	2.75	MA	MS	1
3. INTERPERSONAL STRAIN	2.27	SLA	LS	4

4. PHYSICAL STRAIN	2.74	MA	MS	2
	2.52	MA	Moderately Stressful	

The data shows the category of Psychological Strain acquired the highest composite mean of 2.75, with an interpretation of “Moderately Stressful.” In comparison, the category of Interpersonal Strain acquired the lowest composite mean of 2.27, with an interpretation of “Slightly Stressful. Consequently, the overall mean of 2.52 reports that modular distance learning (MDL) has contributed to moderate levels of personal strain as rated by public secondary teachers of the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC, comprising the districts of Maribojoc, Antequera, Catigbian, Balilihan, and Cortes, Bohol. The present study relates to the findings of Shen and Slater (2021), showed academic staff in a university in Northern Ireland experienced moderate stress levels and distraction behaviors were the most common form of coping mechanism. Moreover, the academic staff experienced moderate status of mental health, with poor emotional wellbeing.

Table 2.3
Level of Occupational Stress on Personal Resources
n=119

Statement	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1 RECREATION				
1. I do not have the opportunities to out-of-town family bonding.	2.41	SLA	LS	4
2. Instead of going out, I prefer to be at home most of the day.	2.56	MA	MS	1
3. I rather spend my time on reviewing my work.	2.52	MA	MS	2
4. I do not have quality time with my colleagues since the outbreak.	2.41	SLA	LS	3
5. I prefer getting connected with my superior in virtual setting.	2.29	SLA	LS	5
Composite Mean	2.44	SLA	LS	
C.2 SELF-CARE				
	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. Seeing a physician for a medical check-up will be stressful.	2.45	SLA	LS	3
2. I need to skip meals to get my work done before the deadline.	2.11	SLA	LS	4
3. Taking too much energy drink is helpful whenever I feel tired.	2.04	SLA	LS	5
4. Avoid eating processed foods.	2.67	MA	MS	2
5. Taking too much coffee in a day is not ideal for my health.	2.97	MA	MS	1
Composite Mean	2.45	SLA	LS	
.3 SOCIAL SUPPORT				
	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. I do not ask help from my colleagues as everybody is busy.	2.36	SLA	LS	5
2. Asking my colleagues for help is my last recourse if needed.	2.73	MA	MS	4
3. I am doing my best to be digitally literate without asking help.	2.93	MA	MS	1.5
4. I tried my hardest of being technically competent on my own.	2.93	MA	MS	1.5
5. I only need assistance from my colleagues when things get worse.	2.73	MA	MS	3
Composite Mean	2.74	MA	MS	
4 RATIONAL/COGNITIVE COPING				
	WM	DV	INT	Rank
1. Parents complaining about their children's grades are annoying.	2.38	SLA	LS	2
2. I rarely make suggestions because I lack self-confidence.	2.05	SLA	LS	4
3. I usually panicked when prioritizing a specific task.	1.92	SLA	LS	5
4. I only refer to my timetable when very necessary.	2.35	SLA	LS	3
5. I have to finish school task at home until I am done.	2.66	MA	MS	1
Composite Mean	2.27	SLA	LS	
Overall Mean	2.47	SLA	Less Stressful	

Parameter:
1.00 - 1.74 Disagree Not Stressful

1.75 - 2.49	Slightly Agree	Less Stressful
2.50 - 3.24	Moderately Agree	Moderately Stressful
3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Highly Stressful

Table 2.3 presents the level of occupational stress among teachers based on four components of Personal Resources: recreation, self-care, social support, and rational/cognitive coping. The overall mean of 2.47 indicates that teachers experienced a Slightly Stressful level of occupational stress in this dimension.

In terms of Recreation, the most stressful item was preferring to stay at home rather than going out (WM = 2.56). The composite mean of 2.44 suggests that limited social interaction and mobility during lockdowns slightly affected teachers' ability to unwind. However, most managed to adapt by finding productive alternatives.

For Self-Care, avoiding excessive coffee was rated highest (WM = 2.97), while reliance on energy drinks was lowest (WM = 2.04). With a composite mean of 2.45, this category also indicated a Slightly Stressful level. Teachers remained health-conscious and mindful of their physical well-being despite work demands.

Social Support yielded the highest composite mean of 2.74, interpreted as Moderately Stressful. Teachers reported trying to improve digital literacy independently (WM = 2.93), reflecting moderate stress due to limited collegial support. This highlights the need for better collaborative structures and mental health support systems.

Lastly, Rational/Cognitive Coping had a composite mean of 2.27, interpreted as Slightly Stressful. Teachers were committed to completing tasks (WM = 2.66) and showed discipline in time management, though some experienced occasional difficulty in task prioritization.

Overall, the findings suggest that while teachers experienced manageable stress levels related to personal resources, efforts to enhance support systems, promote wellness, and encourage collaboration could further reduce their occupational stress during modular distance learning.

Table 2.3.1
Summary on Teachers' Occupational Stress for Personal Resources
n=119

Categories	CM	DV	INT	RANK
1. RECREATION	2.44	SLA	LS	3
2. SELF-CARE	2.45	SLA	LS	2
3. SOCIAL SUPPORT	2.74	MA	MS	1
4. RATIONAL/COGNITIVE COPING	2.27	SLA	LS	4
Overall Mean	2.47	SLA		Less Stressful

The data shows the category of Social Support yielded the highest composite mean of 2.74, with an interpretation of "Moderately Stressful." Conversely, the category

of Rational/Cognitive Coping yielded the lowest composite mean of 2.27, with an interpretation of "Slightly Stressful. Consequently, the overall mean of 2.47 reports that modular distance learning (MDL) has contributed to low stress levels on personal resources as rated by the respondents. The present study relates to the findings of Poysa et al. (2021) who conducted a study in Finland under the title, " Patterns of Teachers' Occupational Well-Being during the Covid-19 Pandemic: Relations to Experiences of Exhaustion, Recovery, and Interactional Styles of Teaching." Findings revealed that during the first few months, many teachers experienced increase in occupational stress. However, teacher's work engagement and performance was not severely affected during the first few months of the pandemic.

Table 3.1
Level of the Respondents' Performance Skills
n = 119

Statement	WM	DV	INT	Rank
A. PERFORMANCE SKILLS				
In modular teaching, I . . .				
1. provided additional learning resources to my students;	3.16	SM	APS	10.5
2. made myself very accessible for school concerns;	3.45	FM	HPS	2.5
3. clearly responded to students' inquiry;	3.55	FM	HPS	1
4. clearly informed students about learning competencies;	3.33	FM	HPS	5
5. provided clear information about modular instruction;	3.45	FM	HPS	2.5
6. engaged my students in group-based activities;	2.70	SM	APS	14
7. encourage my students to practice individualized learning;	3.34	FM	HPS	4
8. did not hesitate to share my views about modular distance learning (MDL);	3.19	SM	APS	8
9. provided initial overview of the subject matter;	3.26	FM	HPS	6
10. facilitated student to student interaction by using online platforms;	2.76	SM	APS	13
11. maintained a very objective position with my students;	3.17	SM	APS	9
12. organized activities that were not included in the modules;	2.60	SM	APS	15
13. efficiently incorporated technologies for communication;	3.11	SM	APS	12
14. provided a good command about my students' performance; and	3.21	SM	APS	7
15. applied an assessment criteria tailored to students' diverse learning abilities.	3.16	SM	APS	10.5
Composite Mean	3.16	Average Psychosocial Skills		

Parameter:
 1.00 - 1.74 Not Manifested Very Low Psychosocial Skills
 1.75 - 2.49 Rarely Manifested Low Psychosocial Skills
 2.50 - 3.24 Sometimes Manifested Average Psychosocial Skills

Table 3.1 presents the respondents' performance skills in modular teaching. The highest-rated statement was "I clearly responded to students' inquiry" (WM = 3.55), indicating strong commitment to addressing students' learning needs despite the absence of face-to-face classes. Other frequently manifested skills included providing clear modular instruction and being accessible for school concerns (both WM = 3.45), reflecting high responsiveness and communication.

Encouraging individualized learning (WM = 3.34) also ranked high, suggesting that teachers promoted independent learning strategies. In contrast, organizing non-module activities (WM = 2.60) and facilitating group-based or online peer interactions (WM = 2.70 and 2.76) ranked lowest, likely due to limited internet access and the constraints of modular delivery.

The composite mean of 3.16 indicates that teachers' performance skills were sometimes manifested, reflecting average psychosocial skills in this area. While individual responsiveness and instructional clarity were evident, collaborative and tech-integrated strategies were less emphasized—highlighting areas for professional development in modular distance learning.

Table 3.2
Level of the Respondents' Interpersonal Skills
n = 119

Interpersonal Skills	WM	DV	INT	Rank
In spite the limited personal interaction, I . . .				
1. easily got the attention of my students.	3.13	SM	HPS	14.5
2. gave a lot of emotional support to my students.	3.16	SM	HPS	13
3. imparted motivations to my students every time we communicate.	3.30	FM	VHPS	10
4. provided clear and constructive feedback on students' performance.	3.38	FM	VHPS	5.5
5. responded immediately through text messaging, phone calls, etc.	3.34	FM	VHPS	8
6. identified the appropriate assistance Needed by my students.	3.35	FM	VHPS	7
7. fully understood about my professional boundaries.	3.53	FM	VHPS	1
8. had a very open-mind in seeking help from my colleagues.	3.38	FM	VHPS	5.5
9. did not have any issues when receiving negative feedbacks.	3.24	SM	HPS	11
10. received social support from my colleagues.	3.22	SM	HPS	12
11. did not hesitate asking for professional advice.	3.42	FM	VHPS	2
12. responded in decent manner when I Received a negative feedback.	3.40	FM	VHPS	3
13. carefully considered the source of feedback before changing my behavior.	3.31	FM	VHPS	9

14. carefully identified situations when making comments.	3.39	FM	VHPS	4
15. commended that having a negative impact on someone is off to me.	3.13	FM	HPS	14.5
Composite Mean	3.31	High Psychosocial Skills		

Parameter:		
1.00 - 1.74	Not Manifested	Very Low Psychosocial Skills
1.75 - 2.49	Rarely Manifested	Low Psychosocial Skills
2.50 - 3.24	Sometimes Manifested	Average Psychosocial Skills
3.25 - 4.00	Frequently Manifested	High Psychosocial Skills

Table 3.2 shows the respondents' interpersonal skills in modular teaching. The highest-rated item was *"I fully understood about my professional boundaries"* (WM = 3.53), reflecting strong awareness and maturity in maintaining professional conduct. Other highly rated responses included seeking professional advice (WM = 3.42) and responding respectfully to negative feedback (WM = 3.40), indicating openness and emotional intelligence.

On the other hand, the lowest-rated items were *"I easily got the attention of my students"* and *"I commended that having a negative impact on someone is off to me"* (both WM = 3.13), suggesting some challenges in student engagement and maintaining positive communication during modular learning.

Despite limited in-person interaction, most teachers showed strong interpersonal capabilities, such as clear feedback, motivation, and collegial support. The composite mean of 3.31 indicates that interpersonal skills were frequently manifested, reflecting high psychosocial skills among respondents. This aligns with the idea that teachers adapted well socially and emotionally despite the constraints of modular distance learning.

Table 3.3
Level of the Respondents' Self-Management Skills
n = 119

Self-Management Skills	WM	DV	INT	Rank
In spite the limited personal interaction, I . . .				
1. kept my focus on modular teaching;	3.21	SM	APS	13.5
2. managed myself towards my goals in teaching;	3.41	FM	HPS	3
3. managed to track my progress at work regularly;	3.42	FM	HPS	2
4. paid close attention to my thoughts about my performance;	3.29	FM	HPS	10
5. managed my behavior in adverse situations;	3.38	FM	HPS	4
6. did my best to stay calm when I fail;	3.32	FM	HPS	9
7. made myself very capable of making clear plans;	3.27	FM	HPS	11
8. set clear standard for myself and for my work;	3.36	FM	HPS	7
9. got myself over hard things so quickly;	3.18	SM	APS	15
10. silently praised myself for a job well done;	3.26	FM	HPS	12

11.gave myself something special after progressed at work;	3.21	SM	APS	13.5
12.motivated myself to be proficient in handling digital tools;	3.34	FM	VHPS	8
13.stayed calm and composed in dealing with adversities;	3.37	FM	VHPS	5.5
14. stucked to my principle on becoming a progressive teacher; and	3.37	FM	HPS	5.5
15. remained passionate and dedicated to my job.	3.51	FM	HPS	1
Composite Mean	3.33	High Psychosocial Skills		

Parameter:
1.00 - 1.74 Not Manifested Very Low Psychosocial Skills
1.75 - 2.49 Rarely Manifested Low Psychosocial Skills
2.50 - 3.24 Sometimes Manifested Average Psychosocial Skills
3.25 - 4.00 Frequently Manifested High Psychosocial Skills

Table 3.3 presents the respondents’ self-management skills in modular teaching. The highest-rated statement was “I remained passionate and dedicated to my job” (WM = 3.51), reflecting strong emotional resilience and commitment. Tracking work progress (WM = 3.42) and setting teaching goals (WM = 3.41) also ranked highly, indicating consistent focus and goal-setting despite the challenges of distance learning.

The lowest-rated item was “I got myself over hard things so quickly” (WM = 3.18), suggesting that some teachers needed more time to recover from difficult situations. Still, most demonstrated good emotional control, motivation, and planning ability.

The composite mean of 3.33 signifies that self-management skills were frequently manifested, reflecting high psychosocial skills among the respondents. Overall, this dimension ranked highest among the three psychosocial skills assessed, followed by Interpersonal Skills (3.31) and Performance Skills (3.16), highlighting teachers’ strong internal coping and emotional regulation during modular distance learning.

Table 4
Level of Teachers’ Job Performance
n=119

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Interpretation
Job Performance	3.50	4.45	4.15	Very Satisfactory

The mean of 4.15 explains a very satisfactory job performance in modular distance learning (MDL), implying competence and dedication at work. Moreover, 100% of the respondents’ population unanimously acquired an IPCR rating within the category of “Very Satisfactory.” Eventually, the result contradicts the study of Lee et al. (2021), which revealed Taiwanese employees had more significant development paths compared to mainland China employees in terms of prior knowledge, organizational support, self-efficacy, employee qualification, subjective well-being, and job performance. To explain

further on the credibility of the unanimous results, the teachers made a self-assessment on their job performance and were validated through principal-teacher conference.

Table 5.1
Relationship between the Respondents' Profile and Occupational Stress

Variables	X ²	df	p-value (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Age and Occupational Stress	10.948	12	.533	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Sex and Occupational Stress	1.627	3	.653	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Highest Educational Attainment and Occupational Stress	6.266	12	.902	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Length of Service and Occupational Stress	10.194	12	.599	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀

Table 5.1 shows that all computed p-values for age (.533), sex (.653), highest educational attainment (.902), and length of service (.599) are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates that none of the respondents' profile variables have a significant relationship with their level of occupational stress. Therefore, the study fails to reject the null hypothesis for all variables.

These findings suggest that occupational stress levels among public secondary school teachers in the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC are not influenced by demographic factors such as age, gender, educational background, or years of service. This contrasts with several previous studies, including those by Mohla (2015), Kuchy and Thilagavathy (2018), and Jiang et al. (2018), which found significant links between these demographic variables and occupational stress across different professional and cultural contexts. These studies highlight how factors such as age, teaching experience, and job type can shape stress levels in varied work environments.

Table 5.2
Relationship between the Respondents' Profile and Psychosocial Skills

Variables	X ²	df	p-value (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Age and Psychosocial Skills	8.224	8	.412	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Sex and Psychosocial Skills	2.592	2	.274	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀
Highest Educational Attainment and Psychosocial Skills	23.012	8	.003	Significant	Reject H₀
Length of Service and Psychosocial Skills	8.478	8	.388	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H ₀

Table 5.2 reveals that among the respondents' profile variables, only highest educational attainment showed a significant relationship with psychosocial skills ($p = .003$). This indicates that educational background plays a key role in influencing teachers' psychosocial competence during modular distance learning. Therefore, the study rejects the null hypothesis for this variable.

In contrast, age ($p = .412$), sex ($p = .274$), and length of service ($p = .388$) all exceeded the 0.05 level of significance, indicating no significant relationship with psychosocial skills. The study thus fails to reject the null hypothesis for these variables, suggesting that psychosocial skills were consistently demonstrated regardless of the respondents' age, gender, or years of teaching experience.

These findings highlight the importance of advanced education in strengthening psychosocial competencies, while also showing that other demographic factors did not significantly impact teachers' psychosocial responses during modular teaching.

Table 6
Correlation of Occupational Stress, Psychosocial Skills,
and Job Performance

Variables	r value	p-value (2-tailed)	Interpretation	Decision
Occupational Stress and Psychosocial Skills	0.158	.086	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H_0
Occupational Stress and Job Performance	0.002	.986	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H_0
Psychosocial Skills and Job Performance	-0.073	.429	Insignificant	Failed to Reject H_0

Table 6 shows that there were no significant correlations among the variables. The correlation between occupational stress and psychosocial skills ($p = .086$), occupational stress and job performance ($p = .986$), and psychosocial skills and job performance ($p = .429$) all exceeded the 0.05 level of significance. These results indicate that occupational stress did not significantly affect either the psychosocial skills or job performance of public secondary teachers in the MACBAC area. Likewise, psychosocial skills did not show a significant influence on job performance. These findings suggest that, despite the challenges of modular distance learning, teachers were able to manage their responsibilities without their performance or psychosocial functioning being significantly impacted by stress.

Table 7.1
Variance in Teachers' Occupational Stress

Variable		SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Occupational Stress	Between Groups	.977	4	.244	1.277	.283
	Within Groups	21.815	114	.191		
	Total	22.792	118			
Result: Insignificant						
Decision: Failed to Reject H₀						

The One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Test illustrated a frequency value of 1.277, with an equivalent p-value of .283 which exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. The result illustrates that the respondents' level of occupational stress remains constant regardless of their educational qualification, considering all of the respondents had to deal with slight to moderate work-related stress during the pandemic. Meanwhile, the study of Lunau et al. (2018) showed European teachers with lower education experienced higher levels of work stress in all countries across the continent. However, the strength of the variances differed in many countries in reference to teachers' participation rates in lifelong learning through integrative school policies.

Table 7.2 depicts the significant degree of variance in the respondents' psychosocial skills when grouped according to their highest educational attainment.

Table 7.2
Variance in Teachers' Psychosocial Skills

Variable		SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Respondents' psychosocial skills	Between Groups	.288	4	.072	0.509	.729
	Within Groups	16.091	114	.141		
	Total	16.379	118			
Result: Insignificant						
Decision: Failed to Reject H₀						

By using the One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Test, the frequency value of 0.509 accumulated a p-value of .729, which exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. The result illustrates there is no variance in the respondents' level of psychosocial skills in modular distance learning (MDL) regardless of their educational qualification. This specific result also suggests that completing a Doctoral or Masteral Degree showed no significant increase or decrease in the level of their psychosocial skills compared to those who earned units in a Master's Degree Program or hold a Bachelor's Degree. On the other hand, the study of Sun and Zhang (2024) obtained a contrasting result. Their findings revealed that higher levels of academic engagement in an online learning

environment significantly influenced EFL learning outcomes among Chinese university students, with notable differences observed based on learners' academic levels.

Table 7.3
Variance in Teachers' Job Performance

Highest Educational Attainment		N	Mean Rank	X ²	df	Asymp. Sig.
Job Performance	Bachelor's Degree	20	48.93	4.139	4	.388
	With Master's Units	78	62.14			
	Master's Degree	17	59.97			
	With Doctoral Units	2	91.75			
	Doctoral Degree	2	55.75			
	Total	119				
Result: Insignificant						
Decision: Failed to Reject H₀						

Using the Kruskal Wallis Test, the p-value of .388 failed to reject the null hypothesis since it is beyond the 0.05 significance level. The result indicates no variances in the respondents' level of job performance in modular distance learning (MDL) when grouped base on their highest educational attainment. One notable reason is that most teachers dealt with the transition in education during the Covid-19 pandemic. The findings contradict the study of Janardhanan and Raghavan (2017), which revealed employee's academic background and length of service have moderating roles with their job performance. Specifically, it showed increased job performance on employees with higher educational attainment and employment experience.

Findings

The study presents the following findings according to sequence of the specific sub-problems.

1. Profile of the Respondents

1.1 Age. The study has a cohort of teachers with a minimum age of 30 years old, comprising 76.47% of the respondents' total population.

1.2 Sex. The study has a cohort of female teachers, comprising 89.08% of the respondents' total population.

1.3 Highest Educational Attainment. The study has a cohort of teachers who earned academic units in a Master's Degree Program, comprising 65.55% of the respondents' total population.

1.4. Length of Service. The study has a cohort of teachers with a minimum length of service of at least 6 years, comprising 72.27% of the respondents' total population.

2. The Level of Teachers' Occupational Stress in the Three (3) Dimensions

2.1 Occupational Role in the Six (6) Components

2.1.1 Role Overload. The composite mean of 3.07 denotes the respondents felt moderate work-related stress level in modular distance learning (MDL).

2.1.2 Role Insufficiency. The composite mean of 2.73 denotes the respondents felt moderate work-related stress level in attending to their job during the temporary suspension of face-to-face classes.

2.1.3 Role Ambiguity. The composite mean of 2.52 denotes the respondents felt moderate work-related stress level in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL).

2.1.4 Role Boundary. The composite mean of 1.73 denotes the respondents felt very low work-related stress level since the teachers and their superior harmoniously collaborated in spite the limited in-person interaction in modular distance learning (MDL).

2.1.5 Responsibility. The composite mean of 2.22 denotes the respondents felt low work-related stress level since the teachers remained committed in attending to their job despite the absence of face-to-face classes.

2.1.6 Physical Environment. The composite mean of 2.37 denotes the respondents felt low work-related stress level since the teachers were responsible in maintaining a comfortable working environment during the pandemic.

In summary, the overall mean of 2.44 denotes the teachers manifested a slightly stressful job experience during the temporary suspension of face-to-face classes as a part of the Philippine government's strong initiatives in containing the rapid spread of the coronavirus disease (Covid-19).

2.2 Personal Strain in the Four (4) Components

2.2.1 Vocational Strain. The composite mean of 2.34 implies the respondents felt a slightly stressful job experience in modular distance learning (MDL) since they performed their duties and responsibilities in the implementation of modular distance learning a highly commendable manner.

2.2.2 Psychological Strain. The composite mean of 2.75 implies the respondents felt moderate work-related stress level in attending to their job during the temporary suspension of face-to-face classes, specifically with students unable to comply requirements on time and the quality of student learning has also attributed the level of teachers' work-related stress.

2.2.3 Interpersonal Strain. The composite mean of 2.27 implies maintain harmonious interpersonal relationships in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL) was slightly stressful only in the presence of a harmonious school environment interaction.

2.2.4 Physical Strain. The composite mean of 2.74 implies the respondents felt moderate work-related stress level in checking the output of the students in modular distance learning (MDL).

In summary, the overall mean of 2.52 implies the teachers manifested a moderately stressful job experience during the temporary suspension of face-to-face classes in dealing with personal strain in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL).

2.3 Personal Resources in the Four (4) Components

2.3.1 Recreation. The composite mean of 2.44 indicates the respondents felt a slightly stressful job experience in modular distance learning (MDL) since they demonstrated self-discipline in doing the usual things during pre-Covid times.

2.3.2 Self-Care The composite mean of 2.45 indicates the respondents felt slightly stressed in attending to their personal physiological needs, specifically in taking good care of their selves during the pandemic.

2.3.3 Social Support. The composite mean of 2.74 indicates a moderately stressful job experience in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL), since the majority of the respondents practiced more autonomy in attending to their job.

2.3.4 Rational/Cognitive Coping. The composite mean of 2.27 indicates the respondents felt slightly stressed in dealing with their coping strategies on the adversities encountered in modular distance learning (MDL).

In summary, the overall mean of 2.47 implies the teachers manifested a slightly stressful in dealing with their personal resources in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL). Thus, the grand mean of 2.48 elucidates that public secondary teachers of the participating district only manifested slightly stressful experiences in providing educational continuity during the academic year 2021-2022.

3. The Level of Teachers' Psychosocial Skills in the Three (3) Dimensions

3.1 Performance Skills. The composite mean of 3.16 explains the teachers demonstrated average psychosocial skills in attending to their job in modular distance learning (MDL), specifically with their performance skills. The result also explains a moderate manifestation of teaching competence in the absence of face-to-face classes.

3.2 Interpersonal Skills. The composite mean of 3.31 explains the teachers demonstrated high psychosocial skills in attending to their job in modular distance learning (MDL), specifically with their interpersonal skills. The result also explains frequent manifestation of a harmonious relationship in the school environment.

3.3 Self-Management Skills. The composite mean of 3.33 also explains the teachers demonstrated high psychosocial skills in attending to their job in modular distance learning (MDL), specifically with their self-management skills. The result also explains frequent manifestation of self-regulation and self-discipline in dealing with the adversities in the new normal education.

In summary, the overall mean of 3.27 explains high psychosocial skills among the respondents in their occupational embodiment to public service by providing educational continuity during the pandemic.

4. The Level of Teachers' Job Performance in Modular Distance Learning (MDL) based on IPCR Results

The mean of 4.15 elucidates a "Very Satisfactory" job performance of the respondents in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL). The result clearly indicates professional embracement since the teachers manifested a commendable teaching performance in spite the abrupt transition in the Philippine education system.

5. The Relationship between the Respondents' Profile and Level Occupational Stress and Psychosocial Skills

5.1 Respondents' Profile and Occupational Stress

5.1.1 Age and Occupational Stress. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .533 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' maturity level did not associate their occupational stress.

5.1.2 Sex and Occupational Stress. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .653 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance,

implying the respondents' categorical distribution according to gender has no association with their occupational stress.

5.1.3 Highest Educational Attainment and Occupational Stress. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .902 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' level of education and occupational stress are not statistically related.

5.1.4 Length of Service and Occupational Stress. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .599 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' length of teaching experience and the level of their occupational stress are not related.

5.2 Respondents' Profile and Psychosocial Skills

5.2.1 Age and Psychosocial Skills. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .412 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' maturity level and the level of their psychosocial skills are not statistically related.

5.2.2 Sex and Psychosocial Skills. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .274 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' categorical distribution according to gender did not associate their psychosocial skills.

5.2.3 Highest Educational Attainment and Psychosocial Skills. The study rejected the null hypothesis since the p-value of .003 is below the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' level of education and the level of their performance skills, interpersonal skills, and self-management skills are statistically related.

5.2.4 Length of Service and Psychosocial Skills. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .388 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance, implying the respondents' length of service and the level of their psychosocial skills are not related.

6. The Correlation of the Study's Main Variables

6.1 Occupational Stress and Psychosocial Skills. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .086 surpasses the 0.05 level of significance. The result implies the respondents' level of occupational stress did not affect the level of their psychosocial skills in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL). Specifically, the two variables are insignificantly correlated since the respondents manifested low levels of occupational stress while they attained high levels of their psychosocial skills.

6.2 Occupational Stress and Job Performance. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .986 surpasses the 0.05 level of significance. The result implies the respondents' level of occupational stress did not affect the level of their job performance since they only felt slightly distracted while they attained a very satisfactory job performance in modular distance learning (MDL).

6.3 Psychosocial Skills and Job Performance. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .429 surpasses the 0.05 level of significance. The result implies the respondents' level of performance skills, interpersonal skills, and self-management skills did not influence the level of their job performance, considering the respondents already demonstrated readiness in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL) for the second time around.

7. Variance in the Respondents' Occupational Stress, Psychosocial Skills, and Job Performance when Grouped According to their Highest Educational Attainment

7.1 Occupational Stress. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .283 exceeds the 0.05 level of significance. The result denotes the respondents' level of occupational stress when grouped according to their highest educational attainment is equal. It also denotes that regardless of being a Doctoral Degree holder or a College Degree holder, the respondents experienced the same level of occupational stress.

7.2 Psychosocial Skills. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .729 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. The result denotes the respondents' level of psychosocial skills when grouped according to their highest educational attainment is equal. It also denotes that regardless of being a Doctoral Degree holder or a College Degree holder, the respondents manifested the same level of psychosocial skills.

7.3 Job Performance. The study failed to reject the null hypothesis since the p-value of .729 surpasses the 0.05 level of significance. The result denotes the respondents' level of job performance when grouped according to their highest educational attainment is equal. It also denotes that regardless of their educational attainment, the respondents attained a very satisfactory teaching performance.

Conclusions

The study concludes that teachers in public secondary schools in the Sub-Congressional District of MACBAC, were resilient in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL), specifically during the academic year 2021-2022. This implication is based on the findings wherein the respondents recognized a slightly stressful job experience during the pandemic. The study also concludes that the teachers were highly committed since they demonstrated high psychosocial skills and very

satisfactory job performance. Further, the respondents' personal profiles are not significantly related to the level of their occupational stress and psychosocial skills, except for highest educational attainment which is significantly related with their psychosocial skills.

Recommendations

Concerning the researcher's program of study, which is educational management, the first set of recommendations are addresses to the school administrators.

1. Public health emergencies like Covid-19 may arise anytime, in this view, school administrators may initiate in developing a school-based preparedness program on teachers' occupational well-being in consideration to the status quo that the teachers are the backbone of any educational system.
2. In overcoming occupational stress among teachers, school administrators are advised to implement a wellness program for teachers' mental health to up-skill and reinvent themselves from job-related stress and burnout.
3. School administrators should ensure a supportive and collaborative organizational culture by conducting time management training to be facilitated by experts in human resource management.
4. School administrators may allocate additional budget for the provision of leisure and learning facilities like e-library, fitness center, and a café inside the school campus to provide the school community with a variety of options in maintaining a sustainable pleasant working environment and improved the quality of work life among teachers.
5. School administrators should maintain a positive workplace condition and provide continuous professional development of teachers by equally involving them in decision-making forums to amplify their capabilities to perform their job competently in spite experiencing daily stress at work.
6. School administrators (school heads and principals) may coordinate with the Schools District Supervisors in planning and crafting an activity design in conducting a workshop seminar on occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance.

Although Covid-19 is no longer a serious threat to the education sector, the following recommendations are valuable in times of implementing educational continuity program in the emergence of another public health emergency and other natural phenomenon.

A. Recommendations for Teachers on Occupational Stress

1. In mitigating stress on Role Overload, teachers are advised to be prompt during the distribution and retrieval of modules to avoid delay and time constraint on module checking and lesson feedbacking. They may also allocate sufficient time in assessing student learning to ensure credible and reliable results.
2. To avoid high levels of Vocational Strain, teachers are suggested to integrate a synchronous online discussion on topics that were hardly understood by the students.
3. In reducing Psychological Strain, teachers are encouraged to strictly enforce a rule concerning the failure to comply and submit requirements. They may also inform the concerned parents through phone calls and through written notices.
4. In reducing stress levels on Physical Strain, teachers should manage their time effectively to avoid working while beating deadlines. They may also engage to physical fitness exercises like jogging and walking every morning to stabilize their stamina and energy at work.
5. In the aspect of Social Support, teachers may seek technical assistance from ICT experts when confronted with unwanted circumstances in using a desktop computer, laptop, printer, and other digital facilities relevant to their job in modular distance learning (MDL).

B. Recommendations for Teachers on Psychosocial Skills

1. Derived from statement no. 12 under Performance Skills, the weighted mean of 2.60 suggested the teachers to integrate independent learning activities that were not included in the modules like journal writing and questioning that enhances student critical thinking skills.
2. Derived from statement no. 6 and no. 10, the weighted mean of 2.70 and 2.76 suggested the teachers to integrate group-based learning activities to promote cooperative learning among students in the absence of face-to-face classes.
3. Derived from statement no. 1 and 15 under Interpersonal Skills, the weighted mean of 3.13 suggested the teachers to create a group chat for the discussion of important matters at school.
4. Derived from statement no. 2 under Interpersonal Skills, the weighted mean of 3.16 suggested the teachers to maintain a positive attitude toward collegial support and in providing emotional support to students in the absence of face-to-face classes.

5. Derived from statement no. 9 under Self-Management Skills, the weighted mean of 3.18 leads the suggestion for teachers to maintain high levels of resilient attitude in dealing with the adversities in modular teaching.

C. Recommendations on Teachers' Job Performance

Although the teachers attained a very satisfactory job performance, the result encouraged them to demonstrate more enthusiasm in modular teaching, especially to teachers with an IPCR result near the threshold performance rating of 3.500. Aside from using printed self-learning modules (SLMs), they may also integrate weekly teacher to student instructional assessment through online discussion via group chatting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The protocol before the study's conduct was observed correctly. The researcher underwent the Research Ethics Committee review procedures and secured the "Clearance to Gather Data" before conducting the interviews to ensure that the process was normally following correct procedures or protocols.

The researcher secured proper permission and consent from the school administrators through an informed consent form, where they affixed their signatures that signified their willingness to participate voluntarily as the respondents of the study. The researcher ensured that the basic principles of research were followed throughout the study. These principles are anonymity and confidentiality, among others. They were informed of their rights as well as the objectives of the study, and they may withdraw their participation anytime they want. They were also assured of the proper data management and utmost confidentiality of the data gathered.

Further, it underwent an integrity test and citation audit to ensure that other researchers did not plagiarize the paper.

IMPROVING TEACHERS' OCCUPATIONAL WELL-BEING: A PROPOSED ACTION PLAN

Rationale

Discussions about teacher's occupational well-being are often dominated by ideas related to stress, demotivation to work, and burnout. This is also often the case with the academic research into teacher well-being, which tends to focus on psychosocial skills, job performance, and even attrition. However, it is important to consider and promote teachers' professional embodiment in a far more holistic way to achieve better outcomes for the school organization, specifically in the implementation of modular distance learning (MDL).

Subsequently, disruptions in education agitated by the emergence of Covid-19 have brought unwanted circumstances in teaching and learning. The abrupt transition from traditional classroom to modular distance learning (MDL) has changed the perspectives of many Filipinos, specifically on the quality of education. More on these, teachers as the backbone of the educational system should also be given a special consideration regarding their condition at work. In this regard, the researcher developed an action plan on improving teachers' occupational well-being. Moreover, this action plan intends to enhance teachers' resiliency in overcoming occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance at the forefront of the pandemic. Hence, these variables are essential components of school effectiveness and organizational productivity at the middle of dire circumstances in the new normal.

Objectives

This action plan aims to attain the following specific objectives:

1. To provide more opportunities in the embodiment of occupational competence by maintaining a stress-free working environment.
2. To appraise teachers' performance skills, interpersonal skills, and self-management skills in attending to their job in modular distance learning (MDL).
3. To appraise teachers' job performance in providing educational continuity during public health emergencies.

Mechanics of Implementation

After the final review of this thesis by the examining tribunal, the researcher will present the output of the study to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor of the participating districts. The researcher will also provide a copy of the thesis to the concerned School Principals and will then discuss shortly about the significant findings of the study and present the Proposed Action Plan.

However, the objectives herein proposed are merely suggestive in nature and the researcher is open for modification in accordance with the prevailing conditions in modular distance learning (MDL). The implementation of the proposed action plan shall be coordinated and shall be in a collaborative effort between the schools' stakeholders and the Department of Education (DepEd).

Schedule of Implementation

The proposed action plan shall be implemented upon the approval of the Schools District Supervisors of the participating districts and the Schools Division Superintendent. Once approved, the researcher will coordinate with the concerned education authorities, including the teachers for the implementation.

Monitoring and Evaluation

1. Means of Verification (MOVs), such as photos, videos, and narratives relevant to the program, shall be included in the monitoring/evaluation processes.
2. All expenses under the action plan shall be monitored at the end of every quarter.
3. Reassessment on teachers' occupational stress and psychosocial skills shall be conducted at the end of the academic year 2021-2022.
4. Another assessment on teachers' occupational stress, psychosocial skills, and job performance shall be conducted during the reopening of face-to-face classes.

IMPROVING TEACHERS' OCCUPATIONAL WELL-BEING: A PROPOSED ACTION PLAN

AREAS OF CONCERN	OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES	PERSONS INVOLVED	RESOURCES NEEDED	BUDGETARY REQUIREMENT	TIME FRAME	SUCCESS INDICATOR
1. Teachers' Occupational Stress	To provide more opportunities in the embodiment of occupational competence by maintaining a stress-free working environment, specifically on role overload, the role of insufficiency, role ambiguity, vocational strain, physical strain, and social support.	Conducting a one-day district-wide awareness seminar on occupational stress. The activity shall be facilitated by a psychologist or an expert related to the field.	Resource Speaker Schools District Supervisors School Principals	Function Hall Laptop White Board	Php 100,000.00 (estimated)	3 rd Qtr. A.Y. 2021 2022	Conducive and Healthy Work Environment Psychological Well-Being Occupational Well-Being
2. Teachers' Psychosocial Skills	To appraise teachers' performance skills, interpersonal skills, and self-management skills in attending to their jobs in modular distance learning (MDL).	Conducting a one-day seminar on improving teachers' psychosocial skills and job performance in modular distance learning (MDL).	Teachers Administrative Staff	Projector Microphone Reading materials Meals and Snacks			Enhanced Teachers' Instructional Skills Collegial Camaraderie Enhanced Self-Management Skills
3. Teachers' Job Performance	To appraise teachers' job performance in providing educational continuity during public health emergencies.	Regular monitoring of teachers' data entry on student performance assessment, compliance, and submission of answered learning modules.	Teachers Parents Students	printed self-learning modules grading sheet compliance record		3 rd quarter of the A.Y. 2021-2022	Higher IPCR Results School Effectiveness Organizational Productivity

REFERENCES

- Bauer, J. C., & Simmons, P. R. (2000). Role ambiguity: A review and integration of the literature. *Journal of Modern Business*, 3(1), 41-47.
- Darrow, S. M., Callaghan, G. M., Bonow, J. T., & Follette, W. C. (2014). The functional idiographic assessment template-questionnaire (FIAT-Q): Initial psychometric properties. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 3(2), 124-135.
- Herrmann, L., Nielsen, B. L., & Aguilar-Raab, C. (2021, June). The impact of COVID-19 on interpersonal aspects in elementary school. In *Frontiers in education* (Vol. 6, p. 635180). Frontiers Media SA.
- Ibrahim, S. (2011). Role of education in civilization.
- Janardhanan, S., & Raghavan, S. (2017). The influence of rewards in enhancing employee performance through psychological empowerment. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 1(2), 106-111.
- Jiang, T., Tao, N., Shi, L., Ning, L., & Liu, J. (2018). Associations between occupational stress and demographic characteristics in petroleum workers in the Xinjiang arid desert. *Medicine*, 97(31), e11543.
- Kuchy, S. A., & Thilagavathy, T. (2018). Influence of demographic profiles on teacher stress: a study on high school teachers. *International Journal of Advanced Research and Development*, 3(1), 574-577.
- Lunau, T., Wahrendorf, M., Müller, A., Wright, B., & Dragano, N. (2018). Do resources buffer the prospective association of psychosocial work stress with depression? Longitudinal evidence from ageing workers. *Scandinavian journal of work, environment & health*, 183-191.
- McNatt, Z., Boothby, N. G., Wessells, M. G., & Lo, R. (2018). Guidance note on psychosocial support: Facilitating psychosocial wellbeing and social and emotional learning.
- Mezo, P. G. (2005). The Self-Control and Self-Management Scale (SCMS): A general measure of self-control and self-management skills. University of Hawai'i at Manoa.
- Mohla, C. (2015). Age and Occupational Stress: A study on IT and Hotel industry employees. *The International Journal Research Publication's*, 223-236.
- Moreno-Murcia, J. A., Silveira Torregrosa, Y., & Belando Pedreño, N. (2015). Questionnaire evaluating teaching competencies in the university environment. Evaluation of teaching competencies in the university. *Journal of New Approaches in Educational Research*, 4(1), 54-61.
- Osipow, S. H., Doty, R. E., & Spokane, A. R. (1985). Occupational stress, strain, and coping across the life span. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 27(1), 98-108.
- Pöysä, S., Pakarinen, E., & Lerkkanen, M. K. (2021, July). Patterns of teachers' occupational well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic: relations to experiences of exhaustion, recovery, and interactional styles of teaching. In *Frontiers in Education* (Vol. 6, p. 699785). Frontiers Media SA.
- Rahmajati, E., Cahyandari, R., Zawawi, A., Octaviani, V. Z., & Ibrahim, M. Y. (2022). Psychological Resilience of University Student During Pandemic Covid 19. *Human Sustainability Procedia*, 2(2), 33-42.

- Shen, P., & Slater, P. F. (2021). The effect of occupational stress and coping strategies on mental health and emotional well-being among university academic staff during the COVID-19 outbreak. *International Education Studies*, 14(3), 82-95.
- Shernoff, D. J., Tonks, S. M., & Anderson, B. (2014). The impact of the learning environment on student engagement in high school classrooms. *Teachers College Record*, 116(13), 166-177.
- Sreekumaran Nair, S. L., & Sommerville, S. (2017). Impact of Organizational Culture on the Indian IT Workforce's Job Satisfaction and Stress: Qualitative Report from SMEs operating in Trivandruam.
- Sun, P. P., & Zhang, L. J. (2024). Investigating the effects of Chinese university students' online engagement on their EFL learning outcomes. *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, 33(4), 747-757.